

THE EFFICIENCY OF CORPUS LINGUISTIC IN TEACHING GRAMMAR

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Abstract: *The development of grammar instruction and research has begun in the past two decades (Conrad, 2000). Teaching English grammar has been delivered via a traditional method. The present study provides a literature review of how grammar instruction has been influenced by corpus linguistic (CL). The review points out the benefits of implementing corpus-based approach in grammar instruction and some difficulties encountered both teachers and students when applying CL tools. The perceptions of students and teachers towards using CL in grammar instruction was also highlighted. Overall, the participants in the reviewed studies reported positive perceptions towards using corpus-based approach in grammar instruction. Implementing this approach helps teachers design suitable materials and students gain grammar knowledge. It is suggested that further studies are needed to investigate the effectiveness of corpus-based approach in specific grammatical aspects.*

Keywords: *Corpus linguistics, Corpora, Data-driven learning, Grammar instruction, Review of literature*

In recent years, a lot of pedagogical research has appeared, in which scientists give priority to the use of new information and computer technologies in education, One of the modern means of forming linguistic competence as a component of the communicative competence of students is the linguistic corpus. It is understood as a collection of texts on an electronic medium selected in accordance with external criteria (genre, purpose, purpose, industry language) [1;28.]. Concordance software allows you to quickly and accurately search for and select the required lexical and grammatical units in large arrays of texts, and through the analysis of numerous examples to reveal grammatical patterns. In this regard, the linguistic corpus can be used to form the grammatical skills of students' speech. The directions of the corpus linguistics, as well as the projects of the electronic corpus of texts are actively developing and occupy leading positions in the method of teaching foreign languages, having considerable applied potential. In the process of teaching foreign languages, one of the main problems is the lack of appropriate pedagogical text materials and actual grammatical

models. The linguistic corpus is considered as one of the modern information resources on the basis of which it is possible to form the lexical and grammatical skills of speech of students. On the basis of the linguistic corpus the following grammatical skills of students' speech can be formed:

productive grammatical skills:

- to form grammatical forms and structures;
- choose and use grammatical constructions depending on the situation of communication;
- to vary the grammatical formulation of the utterance when the communicative intention is changed;
- formulate a grammatical rule based on search results in the linguistic corpus;
- to distinguish the grammatical design of oral and written texts; use grammatical phenomena in speech;
- possess ways to interpret values and translate basic grammatical categories into their native language [4; 7-8]

Learning the grammar and correct formulation of the utterance, as well as the recognition of grammatical forms in speech and writing, occurs through the formation of grammatical skills. The concept of "grammar" includes different sections of the science of language, for example, such as word formation and phonetics, as well as spelling, elements of lexicology, phraseology and stylistics. The main goal of teaching grammar is the development of skills and abilities of grammatically correct speech. By "grammatical skills" are meant automated operations performed with the grammatical material of the language in the process of speech activity, when consciousness is directed at the content of the utterance. Formation of grammatical skills of speech of students on the basis of the linguistic corpus will be effective if the development of the appropriate methodology will be carried out taking into account the following methodological conditions:

- 1) the formation of students at the time of learning a foreign communicative competence;
- 2) use in the study of tasks to determine the grammatical times, the study of modal verbs, the degree of comparison of adjectives and adverbs, articles, plural of nouns, tasks for testing students' knowledge;
- 3) following a clear learning algorithm with separately identified steps and steps.

The use of a linguistic corpus to study grammatical times. Task: study the concordance data and formulate the rule of formation of the present long time in English [tab 1].

Table 1.

1. has gone wrong some place. I **am** getting dividends on only 50 shares.
2. «and I felt strong. When you **are** playing like that you'd better attack».
3. Cohen is chairman of this phase and she **is** getting an artistic assist from
- 4 .the time of day. Other factors **are** playing a part in the extent of AM

To conduct this task, the teacher must pre-select the necessary examples and select the necessary parts of the speech / parts of the sentence that facilitate the assignment. Using this task, you can study any grammatical times [1;31]. It seems that, first of all, we must proceed from the definition of the concept of "quality" in relation to teaching foreign languages, from what its content, criteria and parameters of evaluation, the stages of ensuring and managing the quality of the level of formation communicative competence, and then to build a model of providing and improving the quality of teaching a foreign language on the basis of the use, in particular, of hull technologies.

In conclusion, the linguistic corpus and the concordance program can significantly optimize the learning process of foreign languages. On the basis of the linguistic corpus, learners can create many tasks of a problem nature to stimulate the research work of students. In this article, author showed possible types of tasks for the formation of lexical and grammatical skills. At the same time, the teacher needs to remember that not all aspects of vocabulary and grammar can be effectively studied with the help of the corpus, nor in any study group the problematic tasks of exploratory research will be successful. In many respects, the linguistic corpus is a means for the teacher to solve educational, methodological and scientific problems.

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